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A phenomenological study: The role of management accounting information in the business decision-making process on successful female Balinese entrepreneurs

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Abstract

The research was conducted to explore more deeply the role of management accounting information that is understood in the process of making business decisions by Balinese Women Successful Entrepreneurs and the extent of their understanding which will be the conclusion of this research. The research approach applied to the research is a qualitative approach that is specific to phenomenological studies. The research informants/subjects are Balinese Women Entrepreneurs who have run their businesses before and after the COVID 19 pandemic, with different business characters and specifications and have proven their success. The similarity that emerges from each informant is that there are two themes, namely the decision-making process that goes through several stages to achieve the best final decision and full accounting information, namely to maintain the going concern of the business, always reflecting on past information as a reference and future information to achieve the company's global targets or goals. The results of the manuscript interview data in the textural description of the five informants stated that they understood the importance of the role of management accounting information in the process of making business decisions, structurally each informant expressed his understanding in the implementation of the use of different management accounting information both financial and non-financial in nature. Referring to the title and subject of the study, applying one grand theory, namely decision making theory and feminism theory as a supporting theory. However, for future researchers, the opportunity to develop the grand theory used is still large, for example Masculine Theoretical Decision Making and Feminism Theoretical Decision Making so that the research results are more specific and quality.

Keywords: Management Accounting Information; Decision Making; Balinese Women; Entrepreneurs; Phenomenological Study

1. Introduction

Talking about Balinese women is very beautiful to hear. Considering that Balinese women are amazing figures. Appreciated for their beauty, flexibility, intelligence and expertise in presenting Balinese cultural customs that are so beautiful through the creativity of Balinese art and customs that are second to none. Balinese women have their own uniqueness, known as hardworking, loyal, polite and attractive to tourists. Balinese women are able to carry out Work Life Balance which is a challenge in life, both from the aspects of career, family and social in the form of customs, it is one of the expressions of research (Dian et al, 2019). Behind her dual role, Balinese women are also able to show themselves as reliable and professional entrepreneurs. In this case, Women Entrepreneurs can be defined as women or a group of women who form an organization by accommodating resources, providing employment, organizing, facing challenges and being ready to take risks. Women have a strong instinct to be able to participate in struggling to meet the economic needs of their families. Evidenced by the increasing number of emerging Women Entrepreneurs in Indonesia.

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The phenomenon that occurs and attracts the attention of researchers is that business activities managed by Balinese Women Entrepreneurs are very reliable, well-developed and successful, but many still do not understand that management accounting information plays an important role as a consideration in the process of making business decisions. As mentioned in research (Nur & Ella, 2019) entitled *The role of women's leadership in decision making*, the findings state that women have much higher challenges than men in leading. Affirmed again by (Sri & Retno, 2010), one of the results of his research states that information seeking behavior and business experience are closely related to women in business decision makers. Researchers (Anthony and Reece, 1989: 6) also state that accounting information specifically intended for management purposes is called management accounting information which is used for the functions of strategy formulation, planning, implementation and control for decision making.

Management accounting information has a role to provide an overview of the company's economic situation so that management or business actors can set accurate and appropriate strategies for business development. In addition, the results of research (Rizki and Fathul, 2015: 42) entitled *Mindset of Successful Businesswomen* show that the mindset manifested in behavior: (1) adaptation to constraints, experiences of failure and success (2) social activities (3) cooperation (4) innovation and business development, serves as a guide and the right strategy for success. In addition (Suartha, 2015) in his research revealed that Balinese women entrepreneurs are able to compete in the international market through determination and ability as entrepreneurs who are ready to face risks so that they are motivated to expand the scale of the company. This is proof that Balinese Women Entrepreneurs are able to be creative and successful. From the description above to be more perfect Balinese Women Entrepreneurs should be able to understand that in making business decisions require information - relevant information. Management accounting information is very useful for management in the stage of analyzing the consequences of each alternative action used to make decisions and consider them.

Most Balinese Women Entrepreneurs are familiar with the increase or decrease in cash flow to monitor the development of their business, but they do not understand that there is still a lot of management accounting information such as financial special reports, product and customer analysis reports, budget company performance reports and other management accounting information needed to monitor their business. Management Accounting Information plays a very important role in analyzing the profits or losses experienced by the company and its supporting factors so that the decisions made become more accurate and real as a reflection of achieving company targets. Santrock, (2008: 362) states that decision making is a thought in which individuals evaluate various options and decide on a choice from many options. This statement by Setiadi, (2008: 17) that decision making is a process of situations and conditions. The point is that decision making is a systematic approach to the nature of a problem, the collection of facts and data, the careful determination of the alternatives faced and taking action according to calculations is the most appropriate action. This is where the role of management accounting information helps entrepreneurs in making decisions. Gender is also an influence in terms of decision making. One of the research results (Dani and Chaniago, 2017: 3) states that gender contributes 57.3% to decision making. While 42.7% is influenced by other factors.

How do Balinese women entrepreneurs maintain the going concern of their business, what is the basis used in making decisions, the extent of the meaning of management accounting information in the process of making business decisions and what is done, in the midst of busy Balinese women in their dual role, work life balance becomes a challenge in their lives, but Balinese women entrepreneurs are able to prove their success in the business world both locally and internationally. This inspires the author to conduct further research and gives the author confidence that research with the title *Interpreting the Role of Management Accounting Information in the Decision-Making Process for Balinese Women Entrepreneurs* is still very feasible and interesting to research.

2. Methods

This study uses a qualitative approach based on the philosophy of positivism or interpretive, namely a naturalistic qualitative research approach whose process is inductive, the data obtained is qualitative data, which still needs to be interpreted so that its meaning can be understood. In terms of qualitative methods, Steven & Jennifer (2002) state that qualitative research deals with data that is not numbers, collecting and analyzing data that is narrative in nature. According to Creswell (2009) qualitative research means the process of exploring and understanding the meaning of individual and group behavior or humanitarian issues. The research process includes making research questions and procedures that are still provisional, collecting data from informants, analyzing data inductively, building partial data into themes, and then providing interpretations of the meaning of data whose final activities make reports into flexible structures. The qualitative approach used in this research is a phenomenological approach. Creswell (2012) states that phenomenological research is a qualitative strategy in which researchers identify the essence of human experience about phenomena as described by informants in a study. Phenomenological is one type of qualitative research, where researchers collect data by participant observation to find out the essential phenomena of participants in their life

experiences. So Phenomenological research explores people's consciousness based on their perceptions, memories and experiences of an event. Phenomenological studies end with drawing the essence of a meaning from research. The phenomenology used in this research is Interpretative phenomenology. This research observes the phenomenon in running their business activities whether Balinese Women Entrepreneurs understand that management accounting information is important in the decision-making process.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Management Accounting Information in Relation to Decision Making

There are three types of management accounting information, namely Full Accounting Information, Differential Accounting and Responsibility Accounting which represent 3 (three) themes out of 12 (twelve) in this study. These three types of management accounting information contain accounting information both qualitatively and quantitatively, both for the past and the future regarding income, costs, assets concerning all company activities including the accountability reports of each division within the company. Management accounting information is information needed by company management for reference in deciding. The role of accounting information in decision making is that management can define problems, separate alternatives from one another, explain the consequences of the chosen alternative and assist management in analyzing and assessing the various alternative actions chosen. Of the three-management accounting information above, Balinese women successful entrepreneurs, especially those who are informants in this study, the five informants theoretically cannot explain what management accounting information is, but in the delivery of meaning from experience in business practice, all informants unconsciously use management accounting information in the decision-making process. The five informants revealed structurally that management accounting information plays a very important role in making business decisions, besides there are other factors that become a reference in choosing various alternatives in decision making.

3.2. Decision Making as a Form of Implementation in Business

The three types of decision making, namely strategic decisions, tactical decisions and operational decisions, are actually inseparable in their implementation. The thing that distinguishes is in terms of the decision maker and the purpose of the decision. But globally all three play a role in running a business. Likewise in this study, of the five informants, each of whom has a business with different specifications, informant one is a producer of herbal products under the Bali Tangi brand, informant two is a retail and wholesale entrepreneur as well as production under the Kaori brand, informant three is a restaurant, bar, villa and resort Bali & Lombok entrepreneur, informant four is also a restaurant, hotel and property entrepreneur and the fifth informant is a well-known footwear product manufacturer, namely shoes under the Ni Luh Djelantik brand, in running his business, there are three types of decision making, both strategic, tactical and operational. Tactical decision making is structurally revealed from the five informants in their interpretation that has to do with the decision-making process so that the theme of competitors and innovation appears, by informants one, two, three and five. So competitors do not make obstacles for informants, instead they become friends, which can increase the productivity of informants racing to work even more superior, not stopping product innovation so that they continue to be superior in the face of business competitors. Strong and weakness is a theme that emerges from the meaning of informant four's experience in the business process, to face competitors and maintain business we must know what strengths or advantages we have and what our weaknesses are so that solutions are needed to cover weaknesses and improve them and maintain the advantages already owned by the company in maintaining a business.

3.3. Decision Making Theory as a Reference for Entrepreneurs in Decision Making

Decision Making Theory refers to the results of research data analysis, the five informants in the decision-making process are more related to the theory popularized by Herbert Simon (1957), namely limited rational theory that each individual or group has limited rational decisions, namely cognitive limitations, imperfect information, and time constraints. By realizing the limitations, informants try to make optimal decisions to solve the problems that arise. As for the decision-making process, all informants undergo the same process, namely through the phase of searching for problems or information, creating alternative solutions to problems, selecting the best alternative from several good alternatives that have been proposed and implementing the final decision.

3.4. Characteristics of Feminism Theory

The word feminism is synonymous with women. The five informants in this study are Balinese women entrepreneurs who daily manage companies which of course have different characters but with the same experience. The interpretation of the phenomena faced is also different. From the structural description of informants one, two and

three revealed that in terms of decision making in particular, women are more sensitive, stronger instincts than men. Women's decisions have more feelings, said informant one (MP1-24). Women have stronger instincts, in emotional conditions, for example, women can still be patient in making decisions, said informant two firmly. Another informant three innocently conveyed that we are grateful to be a woman because women can feel empathy, feel more so that decisions are made more wisely, on the other hand assertiveness is still needed. The results of the study found the theme "Strong Instincts and More Feeling" and this is one of the characteristics of feminism theory characteristics written by namely sensitive to the needs of others, sensitive, sensitive and caring able to capture the feelings of others and realize their needs. In terms of decision making, the results will be better, can minimize the risks that might occur. While the second characteristic emerged from the informant's expression, namely the soft nature possessed by a woman. In terms of a business led by a woman, there is definitely a soft side. From the direction of decision making there is also softness, and the assertiveness of a woman also colors the leadership of a woman, that is the advantage of women being able to balance their softness and assertiveness so that conditions are cooler and more peaceful, not necessarily burning, having to be hard and others and the decisions taken become more real describing the existing conditions.

4. Conclusion

Research that has been conducted on five Balinese female successful entrepreneur informants who are the subjects of this study are extraordinary Balinese women, unique and resilient Balinese women are admirable figures appreciated for their beauty, flexibility, intelligence and expertise, hardworking, polite in living their dual role with a customary environment that is second to none, of course, each has a different character and scope of business has proven itself as a reliable and professional Balinese female successful entrepreneur. This makes it unique and interesting to study. Informant one is a producer of herbal products under the Bali Tangi brand, informant two is a retail and wholesale entrepreneur as well as a product manufacturer under the Kaori brand, informant three is a restaurant, bar, villa and resort entrepreneur in Bali and Lombok, informant four is a restaurant, hotel and property entrepreneur in the Ubud area and its surroundings and the fifth informant is a producer of internationally renowned footwear products, namely shoes with the local brand Ni Luh Djelantik.

From the results of the research answering the formulation of problems related to the meaning of the role of accounting information in the business decision-making process formed 6 (six) emerging themes from the expression of the meaning of each informant, namely past information and future information, standard operational procedures and key performance indicators, competitors & innovation, decision-making process, behind the tenderness of a woman, the sixth is a woman's tenderness.

Softness of a woman, the sixth is strong instinct and more feeling. Related to the concept of decision-making theory and feminism theory, 7 (seven) themes are formed in this study, namely full accounting information, responsibility accounting, operational decisions, types of tactical decisions, limited rational theory, soft and sensitive to the needs of others are 2 (two) categories of feminism theory.

Related to the business decision-making process of successful Balinese women entrepreneurs as the answer to the first problem formulation, the informants' interpretation of the role of accounting information in the business decision-making process in the textural description revealed that they understood. In accordance with the results of the research, the flow of the business decision-making process conveyed by the five informants shows similarities but through a varied process, namely starting from extracting information from various sources both internal and external to find the main problem, analyzing the cause and effect of the problem, then identifying the problem, giving each department in the organization the opportunity to find good alternatives for solving the problem, then the alternative development process is carried out which includes the process of understanding the problem and finding solutions and testing these alternatives. In the end, successful Balinese women entrepreneurs as owners or leaders of companies always take the time to discuss with the management team during their extraordinary busyness are still able to select the best alternative from the best alternatives that have been considered together and evaluate these alternatives, to be immediately implemented as the final result of business decisions.

The results of the research as an answer to the second problem formulation of the interpretation of successful Balinese women entrepreneurs on the role of management accounting information in the process of making business decisions in textural description revealed by all informants that they interpreted the utilization of management accounting information in the process of making business decisions. It is stated that management accounting information is broad in scope and very important in its role in the decision-making process, although almost all informants cannot describe in theory the accounting information reflected in business practices and the decision-making process that has been expressed by all informants in this study.

Structurally, the description of successful Balinese women entrepreneurs interpreting the use of management accounting information in making business decisions is revealed by the five that the use of management information in their business practices is not all management accounting information applied in their business. All informants use but the management accounting information used varies depending on the extent to which their implementation adjusts to the conditions or scope and specifications of their respective businesses and the objectives to be achieved. Management accounting information whose presentation is financial in nature, namely profit and loss statements, balance sheets, statements of changes in capital, budgets, cost of goods sold calculations, selling price calculations, cost calculations and others play a very important role in analyzing company performance. While management accounting information presented in a non-financial manner such as accountability reports of each section in the form of results achieved, obstacles faced and how they propose for the future, standard operation procedures as a reference in operational activities, KPI (key performance indicators), competitor information and decisions on what innovations will be driven and other management accounting information is very important in determining future steps or the future. Both of these management accounting information which in business practice all informants as business people realize that it is very important to be able to make decisions more precisely and directed in achieving the company's overall goals or objectives.

Considering the subject of this research, namely five Balinese women from emerging themes that arise from the experience of phenomena interpreted by all informants, in the management of the company cannot be separated from the nature of feminism that has become the nature of a woman. Judging from the characteristics of feminism theory, there are differences between men and women, especially in decision making. In leading and making decisions, in particular, women have stronger instincts and feel more than men. Women can think of unexpected things that affect decision making and women are more sensitive so that they can minimize the risks that might occur, even though in emotional conditions women can still be clear in their minds in making decisions. Balinese women successful entrepreneurs with multiple roles played in their daily activities and limited time owned, which allows the many challenges that are present in their lives, but Balinese women as entrepreneurs by using accounting information as a reference in the process of making business decisions, can still prove their success.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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